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Sound in Motion

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PROSOUND LAB

MOBILE LOUDSPEAKERS AS AN ALTER EGO

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ABSTRACT

In electronic music, sound, space, spatial sound, and sound movement are pivotal. Our research aims to enrich sound distribution by developing a system that generates sound movements through effective movement of the sound source. This required collaboration across technicians, mechanics, engineers, programmers, and composers. The outcome is a system allowing mobile loudspeakers during chamber music concerts, expanding sound into new acoustic realms and creating variable sound spaces. This greatly enhances the listening experience, freeing listeners from fixed positions. The interaction of the mobile speaker system with music creates a dynamic theatrical and choreographic interplay, with speakers acting as musical alter egos.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Foreword

Artistic music research aims to enhance the auditory and performative aspect of the performer-audience relationship. One way to achieve this is by creating music where sound, typically from fixed sources with simulated movements, is perceived as physically moving due to real motion. Over the past decades, several sound systems have been devised to simulate sound movement virtually. Additionally, some systems have used moving sound sources, originally designed for non-musical artistic performances, to physically create sound motion (refer to Chapter 2: State of the Art).

1.2 Goals

Our main research goal is to create a sound system where speakers move as sound sources within chamber music, expanding music's interaction with the audience. This development, undertaken at the *Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology* in Zurich (ZHdK) during 2021/22, has broad implications for multiple research areas. Key questions arising from this project include:

What's the link between real-space sound movements and the perception of motion from virtual sounds produced by stationary speakers? How do moving speakers interact with motionless acoustic instruments? What are the listener's responses to sounds moving in space compared to simulations from stationary sources? How does our perception of music change when familiar static sound sources begin moving?

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1.3 Concrete object of the research

The mobile sound system's development was inspired by the *Heldendämmerung* concert project, featuring a piano trio, quadraphonic system, and three mobile speakers.

These speakers can move among the audience using radio-controlled vehicles and perform other *local* movements on the vehicle: rotation, combined two-axis polar motion, or elevation (refer to Figure 1). The team included two composers who contributed to the technology and engineering aspects of the research for musical applications.

1.4 Motivation and new domains

The technical advancements stemmed from the requirements of music production and were refined through multiple perceptual experiential workshops, uncovering both challenges and potentials. The impactful presence of mobile speakers not only expanded the auditory dimension but also introduced a concurrent theatrical and choreographic element. These mobile entities assumed a mediating role, akin to personalities, between musicians and the audience. The quest to enrich these novel dimensions of music reception spurred further technical innovations aimed at enhancing perceptual, musical, and theatrical values. The objective was to ensure that the technology seamlessly addressed these diverse aspects, guaranteeing reliable and silent vehicle movement while delivering high-quality, immersive sound to enhance the experience of sound source movement.

1.5 Why all this?

Composition: Develop a system for composers to enhance music and performance across mono, stereo, or quadrasurround (virtual) setups, integrating real acoustic instrument sounds with dynamic moving sound sources.

Perception: Deepen understanding of mobile sound source perception, enriching music recognition and experience in novel contexts while offering composers new creative avenues.

Education: Train a new generation of artists through study and research opportunities, including doctoral positions for composers, choreographers, and others.

Production and Research: Address critical issues in mobile sound source systems to support research and production centers in creating and advancing similar systems. Document the technology and its perceptual implications to encourage wider use and garner improvements from external users.

2. STATE OF THE ART

2.1 Moving speakers as effect devices (1940-1960)

Spatial sound and sound movements are crucial in acoustic and electronic music creation and perception. In the 1950s, Pierre Schaeffer and Jacques Poullin introduced the *pupitre d'espace*, enabling sound distribution across four speakers via gestures during playback of recordings [1, 2].

Karlheinz Stockhausen introduced space as the fifth parameter (sound location) in music [3], allowing precise positioning and movement of sonic events in serial music. In the past, limited studio technology and lack of effect devices meant that rapid or fluid sound movements and the Doppler effect were achieved only by physically moving speakers. For instance, Stockhausen utilized three rotating tables in works like *Kontakte* (1959), *Hymnen* (1967), and *Sirius* (1975), exploring non-musical effects such as motor hum, brake squeaks, and wind noises [4].

2.2 Moving speakers as a design tool (from 1960)

Since the 1960s, speakers have been moved not just due to the absence of effect devices but driven by artistic considerations. This shift occurred because the artistic simulation of a moving sound source became possible and could not be adequately substituted. The moving speaker has become a fundamental element in both visual and musical design, transforming from an invisible playback device to the focal point of spatial sonic presentations, essentially becoming an instrument or sonic personality.

An early example of mobile speakers is found in David Tudor's *Bandoneon! (a combine)* (1966), where his *Instrumental Loudspeakers* [5] move on five remote-controlled platforms [6, 7, 8]. Christian Clozier and Jean-Claude le Duc developed *Les Antonymes* from 1974 onwards, mobile sound and image structures acting as a counterpoint to the fixed speakers of the *Gmebaphone* [9]. Alvin Lucier, in *Words on windy corner* (1980), shifts speakers on carts, altering the spatial relationship between microphones and speakers [10].

Echo Moiré (2011) by Matteo Marangoni resembles our project [11]: Two wheeled horn speakers enact a *robotic opera-ballet*. The space functions as a musical instrument, with bursts and clicks emanating from the speakers, revealing and amplifying the acoustic properties of the surroundings.

3. OUR MOBILE SPEAKERS

Three mobile speakers are utilized in the *Heldendämmerung* concert. They comprise a **mobile platform** with an attached **loudspeaker**. The platform, serving as a subwoofer, remains consistent across all three models, whereas the speakers vary in their movement capabilities.

3.1 Mobile platforms - spatial movement

The carriage is powered by two unsteered stepper motors, with the third wheel being an omnidirectional wheel that stabilizes the vehicle. Small rollers on the running surface enable movement in all directions by turning at right angles. Differential speeds of the two drive wheels dictate the direction of travel. Control is achieved via a steering

Figure 1. The names of the speakers are derived from its movement. Left: *Angela* from tilt and pan (aggregat). Center: *Eliane* from elevation movement. Right: *Roger* from rotation.

wheel and two pedals for forward and backward motion. These vehicles are utilized to position and maneuver the speakers within the space.

3.2 Loudspeaker - local movement

To direct sound precisely, the speakers on the platforms are movable, known as *local movement*. The first platform features a rotating directional loudspeaker that emits sound in a specific direction, offering infinite rotation in both directions or precise alignment (refer to Figure 1: *Roger*). The second platform includes a speaker that swivels and tilts horizontally and vertically by 340 degrees using two servomotors (refer to Figure 1: *Angela*). The third platform has a bar with three small speakers that can be raised and lowered (refer to Figure 1: *Eliane*).

3.3 Control and audio transmission

The vehicles are remotely controlled via WLAN, with a designated driver for each vehicle managing *spatial movement*. In contrast, *local movements* of the speakers are controlled by live electronics patches. This approach ensures precise synchronization with the musical content, which is crucial and cannot be achieved manually.

Audio transmission occurs through radio links, with mid and high frequencies emitted via the moving speaker. Low frequencies are directly transmitted to the vehicle's housing, designed as a subwoofer, through a built-in transducer.

3.4 Path finder

The drivers navigate the platforms along predefined routes marked with adhesive tape on the venue floor (refer to Figure 2a). A camera on the speaker pole allows the driver to maintain control of the vehicle and its path, even if direct visibility is lost (refer to Figure 2b). This camera wirelessly transmits a live view of the vehicle and the immediate area in front of it to the driver, enabling them to follow the adhesive strips accurately.

4. OUTCOME (RESULTS)

An important result was the enhancement of physiological values of sound perception and thus induced musical values. This fact also makes these values accessible to a larger spectrum of users (independent of cultural background).

Figure 2. a) Driving lanes are indicated in white. b) Camera.

The results of the project are then shown below sorted into the different sectors involved.

4.1 Sound system with mobile sound sources

An audio diffusion system was developed for a chamber music ensemble with live electronics, optimizing interaction across three acoustic propagation levels: musicians with acoustic instruments (Absolut Trio: violin, Bettina Boller; cello, Judith Gerster; piano, Stefka Perifanova); amplified audio and live electronics on a quadraphonic system; and amplified audio and live electronics on a mobile speaker system (three radio-controlled vehicles capable of local sound source movement).

The *Heldendämmerung* project, featuring compositions tailored for this system, has been performed four times. A key musical objective is crafting vibrant sound spaces and corresponding virtual scenarios, resulting in dynamic and ever-changing soundscapes. These endeavors occasionally transform temporal and spatial perception into an ethereal, timeless ambience, achieved through the floating recognition and localization of individual sound elements (e.g., slow motion and spatial ambiguity).

Monitoring audience perceptions has provided valuable insights into perceptual values. This expanded understanding of the physiological aspects of music perception offers composers fresh avenues and enhanced interactions with audiences when conceptualizing and composing music.

4.2 Hall setting up

To enhance the expressive capabilities and functionality of the mobile speaker system, a hall setup model was devised to delineate movements within the space: audience islands, vehicle pathways between islands, and crossing points (see Figure 3a).

Figure 3. a) Setting concert hall. b) score instruments. c) vehicle movements. (* = audience island)

4.3 Notation

The movement of the vehicles were notated in the score as well as in a diagram (see Figure 3b) or also as verbal dis-

cription. For both case there was a separate driving score specifically detailing vehicle movements, aimed at drivers (see Figure 3c).

Additionally, we integrated instructions for local movements executed through live electronic commands (Max) transmitted via WLAN.

4.4 System constraints and possible solutions

From concerts and workshops, we learned about constraints and potential solutions for system improvement:

The system faced physical limitations such as speed, stability, noise, accuracy, and safety concerns in moving within the audience. The solution involved enhancing mechatronic engineering, motion control, and programming systems.

Each audience position required a tailored listening experience. This was addressed by ensuring a uniform distribution of spatial motion effects in composition.

Managing spatial movements in the hall necessitated multiple vehicle drivers, each responsible for a specific area. This challenge was tackled by implementing automatic lane following, executing driving commands, avoiding collisions through autonomous systems (AI), and using RFID chip bands on lanes for position detection.

5. VISITOR SURVEY

Among the 114 concert visitors during four concerts, 61 completed and returned the questionnaire.

5.1 Variable sound spaces

Loudspeakers combine to form a sound space over an area. With moving sound sources, this space can vary as speakers on vehicles shift in the hall, altering the space between them. Three speakers can ideally create a triangle, but when integrated with the quadraphonic system’s fixed speakers, the possibilities multiply. The variable sound space is no longer confined to the three mobile speakers’ area; it expands through different fixed and mobile speaker combinations.

Figure 4. Survey results.

In the survey, 59% of participants responded negatively to the question *Have you ever encountered the term 'variable sound spaces'?* (Figure 4a). However, 82% acknowledged familiarity with the term *variable sound spaces* when asked *Have you perceived 'variable sound spaces'?* (Figure 4b). Just 2% claimed they had not perceived *variable sound spaces*.

It's unclear if respondents understood *variable sound spaces* as defined in the project or if they interpreted other perceived situations as such, potentially explaining the high agreement rate.

5.2 Dependence on the seat

Mobile speakers offer the advantage of localized sound, irrespective of seating position, eliminating the need for a traditional sweet spot. How does this impact the overall listening experience?

On the one hand, the perception of the sound field depends on individual listening habits. People who frequently attend concerts may look for a central location in order to enjoy the best possible sound. However, if the mobile speakers are used and their location changes, this can lead to confusion and give the impression that they are not always in the best position.

Individual's perception of the sound field is influenced by their listening habits. Concertgoers often seek a central spot for optimal sound. Yet, with mobile speakers altering positions, this can cause confusion and the feeling that the speakers aren't always optimally placed.

The responses to the question *Did it matter where you sat?* regarding the perception of mobile speakers fall out accordingly (see Figure 4c).

6. CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the use of mobile speakers presents both pros and cons. Considering individual listening habits and speaker visibility is crucial for an optimal experience. While the mobility of speakers offers a fresh way to perceive sound, it necessitates adjustments to seating choices and can pose challenges for visual immersion.

Unexpectedly prominent in the project was the theatrical and choreographic influence of the mobile speakers. In concerts, they became a visual alter ego of musicians, amplifying or distorting acoustic features akin to a magnifying lens, adding a unique dimension to the performance.

6.1 Insights

This project uncovered numerous new phenomena, particularly intriguing is the mechanics of perception within this audio system, offering composers fresh insights and compositional avenues. It's clear that further exploration is warranted across various domains. Below are the guiding research questions:

What happens when moving speakers become visible during music listening? Can changes in brain activity be detected in the relevant areas? Is there a neurophysiological impact of moving speakers on listening? Are there physiological indicators of acceptance or rejection of moving speakers (akin to food preferences or aversions)? Can we infer ways to design movements that enhance acceptance in cases of rejection? Alternatively, should efforts concentrate on reinforcing existing acceptance? Do cultural influences shape how moving speakers are perceived, directed, or understood? What specific cultural imprints might play a role?

6.2 Impressions

Three composers in this project have stated as below what was very different for them to compose for different kind of *time-space relations* than usual; here the perception is diverse; necessity of sound dramaturgical concept.

6.3 Outlooks

Improving vehicles with mobile speakers involves quieter movement and enhanced sound quality. Extensive studies are needed to understand the perceptual effects of moving sound sources, involving experts from diverse fields. This includes refining existing speakers and incorporating technical advancements such as artificial intelligence for motion control and more mobile speakers for better sound coverage. Additionally, exploring new topics in music perception through psychoacoustic and neuroacoustic research is essential.

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